

PRODUCTIVITY OF OKRA UNDER DIFFERENT LEVELS OF POULTRY MANURE AND
PLANT POPULATION DENSITY

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ABSTRACT

Two field experiments were conducted in 2011 and 2012 rainy season at the experimental field of National Horticultural Research Institute, Mbato sub-station, Okigwe, Imo State to investigate the productivity of Okra under different levels of poultry manure and plant population density. A factorial combination of four levels of poultry manure (0.4, 8 and 12t/ha) and three levels of population density (1, 2 and 3 plants/stand) were investigated. The experiment was a split –plot design laid out in RCBD replicated three times. The analyzed data revealed productivity of Okra were enhanced by increasing Okra plant population together with application of poultry manure. The application of 8t/ha of poultry manure gave the highest fruit yield value of 12.40t/ha and 12.49t/ha respectively in 2011 and 2012, in both trials, 12t/ha of poultry manure contributed only marginally. While Okra grown at 3 plants/stand gave the maximum fruit yield of 15.04t/ha and 14.24t/ha for 2011 and 2012 respectively above that of 2 plants and 1 plant/stand/. From the experiment, it seems 8t/ha of poultry manure and 3 plants per stand enhanced the productivity of Okra at Mbato, Okigwe Zone, as sole crop.

KEYWORDS: Fruit-yield, Okra, Poultry manure, Population density, Productivity

Received for Publication: 15/04/13

Accepted for Publication: 27/06/13

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INTRODUCTION

In Nigeria and especially in the South eastern Zone, Okra is grown because of its economic value and this is carried out by subsistence farmers who do so in combination with other crops. The young immature fruits are important fresh fruit that can be consumed in different forms. They could be boiled, fried or cooked. Okra mucilage is suitable for medical and industrial application. It has medically found application as a plasma replacement or blood volume expander (PROTA, 2004). Industrially, Okra mucilage is usually used to glaze certain papers and also useful in confectionery among other uses (Markose and Peter, 1990)

Worldwide production of Okra as fruit vegetable is estimated at six million tonnes per year. In West Africa, it is estimated at 500,000 to 600,000 tonnes per year (Burkill, 1997). Farmers who cultivate Okra are concerned with high fruit yield, since seeds and type of fertilizer to be used form a significant portion of the cost of production. With the current exorbitant price and scarcity of inorganic fertilizer, there is need to develop a sustainable soil fertility management strategy through the supply of sufficient organic manure for optimal Okra yield which also is less harmful on the soil and environment. Poultry manure is a good supplement for inorganic fertilizer since it is cheap and more readily available soil nutrient base, whose pattern of nutrient release is slow (Akanni and Ojeniyi, 2007)

Plant population is a good determinant of the productivity of Okra. Number of plants per area of ground and spacing of plants over the ground are two important features of population density. These properties are necessary to prevent over or under utilization of available resources especially soil nutrients which are inadequate in Nigerian soils (Agboola, 1982). As a result Okra is planted and spaced according to the type of cultivar, with closer spacing being used for dwarfs types than for taller ones (Kemble et al, 1995). Planting at more than one plant per stand has the potential of increasing total plant population per hectare with appropriate

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spacing which invariably may lead to higher yield per hectare; also it is possible to cultivate Okra with more than one plant per stand at a particular spacing. It is therefore of interest to compare its performance at one plant /stand with higher numbers of plants/stand. Therefore, scanty information on optimum levels of poultry manure and population density of Okra grown in the south east, necessitate the need for this trial, as to ascertain the optimum population density of Okra and poultry manure for Okra productivity as a sole crop in Mbato, south-east Nigeria.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The experiment was conducted during the rainy season of 2011 and 2012 at the research farm of National Horticultural Research Institute (NHORT) Mbato, Okigwe (Lat 5° 33' N Long 7° 23' E and 130m above sea level). The soil was sandy loam (743g/kg sand, 155g/kg silt, 122g/kg clay) characterized by low organic matter, low CEC and are highly leached. The area enjoys 1200mm of rainfall with varying temperature. The land was slashed, ploughed and harrowed, then plots were marked out. The experiment was a split-plot design laid out in RCBD replicated three times with poultry manure rates assigned to sub-plots. The treatment consist of four levels of poultry manure, 0,4,8 and 12 t/ha corresponding to 0, 6.9, 13.8 and 20.7 kg /17.28 m² ground area combined with three population densities of Okra, 1 /plant/stand, 2 plants/stand and 3 plants/stand to give 41,667, 83,333 and 125,000 plants/ha respectively with a spacing of 40cm x90cm. Poultry manure collected was applied four weeks before the Okra seeds were sown in order to enhance its proper decomposition and prevent toxicity effect on the Okra seedling. After two weeks of sowing, the okra seed (NHAE-47-4) were thinned down to the required number of plants per stand and population densities. The plots were maintained weed free throughout the duration of the trial.

Data were collected on fruit yield and number of pods, and subjected to analysis of variance (ANOVA) using SAS statistical package (2002 version) and means separate by LSD. Farm gate prices of the harvested crops were obtained. Monetized aggregate yield was calculated as the productivity (Ikeorgu, 2002)

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In both years, 2011 and 2012, 8t/ha of applied poultry manure gave the highest value of fresh fruit yield when compared with other application in 2011, 8t/ha poultry manure gave fresh fruit yield which was 49, 41and 22% higher than when 0, 4 and 12 t/ha were applied respectively (Table 1). In 2012, fresh pod yield at 8t/ha was 43, 33 and 20% higher than when 0, 4 and 12t/ha were applied respectively (Table1). This is attributed to the fact that the Okra plants were able to utilize the nutrients in the poultry manure for yield enhancement and 8t/ha is the Optimum rate required for maximum yield while 12t/ha of poultry manure was over optimal for Okra development (Onyegbule *et al*, 2012). Application of organic manure beyond the optimum level may promote structure development at the expense of reproductive growth (Ojeniyi, 2000).

Okra plants grown at 3plants /stand in both years gave the highest yield value, in 2011, 3 plants/stand gave a yield that is 81.2% higher than 1 plant/ stand and 40.9% higher than that of 2 plants stand while in 2012, 3 plants/stand was 80.6% higher than 1 plant/stand and 41% higher than 2 plants/stand (Table1). This is because the highest plant population density supported maximum marketable yield which is adequate for the land area occupied even though Okra growth and yield was generally enhanced at lower population densities of 1 and 2 plants/ stand. This is in agreement with the findings reported by Odeleye *et al*, (2005).

In both trials, significant interactions were noticed at higher population densities of 3 plants/stand in combination with 8t/ha of poultry manure which gave the maximum fresh fruit yield of 20.36t/ha in 2011 and 20.53 t/ha in 2012 (Table 2). This is an indication that poultry manure at 8t/ha was optimum in supplying nutrient required by Okra plants planted at the population density of 3 plants/stand.

Productivity is expressed as the revenue that could accrue to a farmer from the proceeds of the crop, since productivity is a function of the total production and prevailing market price while increase production is a function of planting materials, seed per hole planted and fertilizer/manure, besides other human and environmental factors. The revenue was significantly higher in both years under 8t/ha of poultry manure and 3

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plants /stand of Okra (Table 3). In 2011, the revenue from sales amounted to N305, 400.00 when 8t/ha poultry manure was combined with 3 plants/ha while in 2012 it was N307, 950 which was higher than N159, 900.00 in 2011 and N164, 250.00 in 2012 for 0t/ha. This may be due to increased fruit yield obtained from the application of 8t/ha poultry manure in combination with 3 plants/stand.

This implies that 8t/ha of poultry manure as soil amendment is the optimum rate required to support the demand placed on the soil to produce significantly higher growth and yield which when combined with Okra planted at 3 plants/stand would maximize land use and hence increase yield per unit area translating to increase productivity. The result therefore shows a positive return to investment and thus it should be recommended for farmers growing Okra in this zone.

CONCLUSION

The planting of Okra at 3 plants/stand in combination with 8t/ha of poultry manure which is regarded as the optimum level of poultry manure would maximize the use of land and increase fruit yield per unit land area hence productivity of the crop in Mbato Okigwe zone.

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Table 1: Effect of Poultry Manure and plant Population Density on pod yield of Okra

Poultry manure rate(t/ha)	Number of Pod/stand in 2011	Fresh pod yield (t/ha) 2011	Number of pod/stand in 2012	Fresh Pod yield (t/ha) in 2012
0	12.44	6.36	10.50	7.13
4	13.33	7.30	12.60	8.32
8	13.67	12.40	14.20	12.49
12	13.50	9.62	14.33	10.01
Mean	13.24	8.92	12.90	9.48
LSD (0.05)	3.92	3.43	1.9	3.22
Okra Population Density/ plant				
1	8.70	2.83	8.78	2.76
2	12.00	8.89	12.30	8.46
3	16.30	15.04	14.15	14.24
mean	12.33	8.92	11.74	8.48
LSD (0.05)	6.48	7.31	4.45	5.8

Table 2: Interaction effect poultry manure and population density on pod yield of Okra

Poultry manure rate (t/ha)	Okra Population density (plant/stand)	Number of pod/stand 2011	Number of pod/stand 2012	Fresh pod yield (t/ha) 2011	Fresh pod yield (t/ha) 2012
0	1	8.43	8.50	2.41	3.58
	2	12.00	10.90	6.02	6.87
	3	13.30	12.00	10.66	10.95
4	1	8.30	9.20	2.21	3.48
	2	11.00	12.80	5.58	6.69
	3	13.46	14.80	14.12	14.77
8	1	10.23	8.00	3.09	3.73
	2	13.30	14.80	13.57	13.37
	3	16.70	16.80	20.36	20.53
12	1	5.60	8.40	3.59	4.25
	2	14.70	11.70	10.40	10.90
	3	15.00	13.70	14.57	14.88
S.E		3.06	0.95	8.49	1.7

Table 3: Effect of poultry manure and population density on productivity of Okra pod (Naira/kg/ha)

Poultry manure rate (t/ha)	Okra Population density (plant/stand)	Fresh pod yield 2011	Fresh pod yield 2012	Productivity (naira/kg/ha) 2011	Productivity (naira/kg/ha) 2012
0	1	2.41	3.58	36,150	53,700
	2	6.02	6.87	90,300	103,050
	3	10.66	10.95	159,900	164,250
4	1	2.21	3.48	33,150	52,200
	2	5.58	6.69	83,700	100,350
	3	14.12	14.17	211,800	221,550
8	1	3.09	3.73	46,350	56,250
	2	13.37	13.57	200,550	203,550
	3	20.36	20.53	305,400	307,950
12	1	3.59	4.25	53,850	63,750
	2	10.40	10.90	156,000	163,500
	3	14.57	14.88	218,550	223,200
S.E		8.49	1.7		

